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Author(s): E. De Matteis, S. Mariotto, T. Lecomte, M. Prioli, S. Sorti, M. Statera, L. Rossi
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DOCUMENT SUMMARY

The report presents the magnet assessment of superconducting accelerator and gantry for the European project HITRI^{plus}. The first section reviews the importance and the prospects of heavy-ion therapy, also mentioning the actual status of world-wide activities. A brief discussion is given on the main technological challenges for magnets in heavy ions accelerators and gantries.

Beside the strong curvature, among the various aspects discussed in this report, the main issues for gantry magnets is the cooling system. The need for a cryogen-free cooling system is challenging, especially aiming at a dipole field of 4 T. This demand can be mitigated with different approaches, ranging from large-acceptance designs to large-margin superconductors. The demonstrator under investigation has been developed accounting for these possible approaches, but the final solution is referred to the following parameters, because they comply with the requirement of integration with actual gantry design.

The main design parameters have been established as common values with two other ongoing programs, IFAST and TERA-NIMMS-SIGRUM. This will allow a fruitful collaboration, with a wider study of magnet design and construction. The basic parameters are: 4 T of dipole field, 0.4 T/s of ramp rate, 1 m of physical length, 80 mm of bore diameter, at least 25 % of loadline margin, and the use of iron yoke and collar.

Different designs have been studied and their performances evaluated. For an easier comparison, a straight geometry has been adopted. Most of the proposed designs are based on canted-cosine-theta (CCT) layouts, three solutions with LTS (Nb-Ti, Nb₃Sn and MgB₂) and one with HTS (ReBCO Tape). A more detailed report is provided for the solution in Nb-Ti, while the subsections about Nb₃Sn, MgB₂ and HTS mainly highlight the peculiarities of each superconductor. A classical cos-theta design in Nb-Ti is also proposed, for the sake of comparing it to the CCT solution.

A set of performance indices to orient the decision of the demonstrator design has been established in terms of costs, power losses and consumption. Additionally, we summarize the mechanical and electrical behaviour of the main support materials, to provide additional information to the further development of the designs. Comparing the CCT and the cos-theta solutions, it can be appreciated that all the main aspects are considerably similar. Cos-theta is negligibly more efficient in the economy of the conductor, but on the other hand it demands for a high current (about 3.5 kA) that increases the current leads power consumption and the cost of the power converter with respect to the CCT in Nb-Ti. Nb₃Sn is a very interesting alternative on paper, but the need for heat treatment is a relevant technological concern. Vice versa, MgB₂ was investigated for the sake of completeness, but the target of 4 T is probably too high for this technology. Finally, the proposed CCT in ReBCO tape may be regarded as a first elaboration of the magnet for a next generation gantry, but it comes with too many technological challenges for a curved demonstrator.

In conclusion, the final remark is to go through for a CCT based on Nb-Ti, suitable to be the basis for the HITRI^{plus} demonstrator magnet.

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1 Introduction

Within the European project HITRI^{plus}, Workpackage 8 (WP8) *Superconducting magnet design* has the objective to perform a first technical and financial assessment of different magnet designs for a novel type of carbon ion synchrotron and gantry complex. This includes a preliminary engineering design of a novel accelerator magnet (mainly combined-function dipoles) and of an innovative gantry magnet. The workpackage also prescribes the manufacturing and test of a small size demonstrator magnet, to give technological feedbacks to the final design of both accelerator and gantry magnets [1]. One of the most demanding aims of WP8 is to get a gantry of about 100 tons weight, which is the 15% of the present reference ion gantry in Heidelberg (600 tons) and less than half of the first world gantry for ions at Chiba (Japan) of about 350 tons [2]. This last facility is shown in Fig. 1.

More specifically, Task 8.1 prescribes a careful assessment of the recent world-wide developments, followed by the proposal of a set of design parameters for the demonstrator. The assessment also considers a possible adoption of HTS superconductors, which are among the most promising solutions for future accelerators. The resulting set of parameters will be the input of Task 8.2. The activity is carried out in close collaboration with WP7, *Advanced Accelerator and Gantry Design*.

Different designs and superconductors have been studied in Task 8.1. For an easier comparison, a straight-magnet geometry is adopted, even if the final magnet design is curved [3], [4]. The study focuses on canted-cosine-theta (CCT) layouts, with both low temperature superconductors (LTS), specifically Nb-Ti, Nb₃Sn and MgB₂, and the high temperature superconductor (HTS) ReBCO. The comparison also includes a cos-theta magnet design based on Nb-Ti.

The following document reports the assessment of magnet design for both fast synchrotron and gantry. The first section summarizes the state of the art of medical accelerators and gantries around the world, highlighting the facilities for heavy ions treatments. The second section discusses the list of the target parameters chosen for the demonstrator magnet. The third section presents the different designs, including a final comparison based on cost, energy efficiency and material indices.

Figure 1: Toshiba superconducting heavy-ion gantry at medical accelerator in Chiba (HIMAC), Japan. Treatment room (top-left), gantry structure (bottom-left), and gantry layout (right). Adapted from [2].

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2 Medical accelerators and Gantry – SoA

The state of the art of medical accelerators and gantry for hadron therapy presented in this section is based on the review of Collings, Lu, Gupta, and Sumption [5]. The reader is referred to their paper for a deepening on the topic.

The use of particles accelerated at a few hundreds of MeV per mass unit for cancer therapy is now an established medical technique. The final goal of particle therapy is not to fully replace conventional X-ray radiotherapy, which requires a smaller and less expensive infrastructure, but to provide the radiation oncologists with an additional tool. In fact, particle beams can treat tumours against which x-ray are poorly effective or guaranteeing a lower survival rate.

The promising features of particle beam therapy are rising the interest in this technology, so that the number of treatment rooms has grown from 140 to 330 in only 5 years (2014 to 2019), and it is expected to reach at least 1200 by year 2030. Consequently, the market value, now of the order of US\$ 1 billion, is projected to US\$ 3.5 to 6.6 billion in 2030.

2.1 Principle of particle beam therapy

The general principle of particle beam therapy, shared with x-ray treatments, is to irreparably damage the tumour cells by irradiating them with a certain amount of energy. The main feature which distinguishes photons (x-ray) and charged particles (proton and heavy ions) is the distribution of delivered energy in the travel through tissues. In fact, charged particles loose energy at a $1/v^2$ ratio, with v being particle velocity. This implies that a relevant fraction of the particle energy is released at the end of the range, resulting in the so-called Bragg peak. Figure 2 shows the energy loss profiles for photons, protons, and carbon ions. The most relevant consequence of this phenomenon is a lower dose of energy delivered to healthy tissues surrounding the tumour, drastically reducing the collateral damage on patient.

Among charged particles, the main difference between protons and carbon ions regards the radiobiological effectiveness (RBE). In fact, photons and protons tend to produce breakage of single strands of DNA, which cells are able to repair. Carbon ions, instead, can produce also unrepairable double-strand breaks. This rises by a factor 3 the RBE of carbon ions against the other radiations, and mainly explains the rising interest in carbon-ions treatment. Nevertheless, carbon ions do not come without costs, as discussed in the next section.

Figure 2: Relative dose versus depth for different radiations, reprinted from [5].

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2.2 Beam handling and technologies

The two main parts of a facility for particle beam therapy are the accelerator and the gantry. The former accounts for accelerating particles up to the desired energy level, while the latter is a rotating structure that directs the beam in a specific spot to strike the tumour.

The main part of the accelerator is the circular path where particles are accelerated by a cyclotron or a synchrotron. The dimensions of this device come from the main particle parameters, in particular the rest mass m_0 , the speed v (with a consequent relativistic correction term γ), and the charge q . To bend a given particle on a circular path of radius ρ , the required magnetic flux density B is found by the so-called magnetic rigidity

$$M = B\rho = \frac{m_0\gamma v}{q}.$$

Both radius and flux density are critical parameters for accelerators: larger radius means larger machine (and so, infrastructure), while higher flux densities require more challenging magnets to be developed and operated. The balance between radius and magnetic field is particularly relevant for the gantry, as far as the machine is rotating and thus the impact of larger radii is critical.

Protons need a beam energy of 220 MeV to reach 30 cm depth. This brings a magnetic rigidity of about 2.3 Tm, so that a 1.5 m bending radius requires about 1.5 T of dipole field. This explains why proton therapy facilities are well served by normal conducting magnets, even if superconductors are still appealing for the construction of very compact accelerators. Ongoing studies are focused on superconducting synchrotrons of very limited size and weight. The Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and ProNova are working on a 2.8-m-diameter, 5-tons synchrotrons which could be directly mounted on a rotating structure, fulfilling the tasks of both accelerator and gantry. The same solution is the baseline for the already-available MEVION S250, a 22-tons synchrotron mounted on a gantry-like structure, so that no beam transport is needed.

Carbon ions reach 30 cm depth with an energy of about 400 MeV/u (or 4.8 GeV in total). Beam rigidity rises to 6.6 Tm. To bend ions on a 1.65 m radius, flux density of 4T is required. This level cannot be reached with normal-conducting magnets. For accelerating synchrotrons, the typical solution is to increase the radius, but for the gantry this is not so trivial to achieve. Therefore, superconducting ion gantries are the preferable solution.

Adopting superconducting magnets for carbon-ion gantry brings additional challenges with respect to fixed accelerators. The main ones are summarized in Section 3, where they are discussed in order to define the main target parameters for the demonstrator.

2.3 Status of medical accelerators facilities

As mentioned at the beginning of this section, the interest in particle therapy is constantly growing. However, out of 24 particle therapy centres in Europe, only four centres employ heavy ions (Carbon ions). Therapy uniquely with proton beams is by far more diffuse. The ratio in the world is 12 ion centres, against 105 particle therapy centres. Despite the discussed advantages, their use is so far limited by the size and cost of the required infrastructure, three to four times higher than for proton-only centres. Almost all proton centres are equipped with gantries to irradiate from multiple directions, improving the treatment effectiveness, while the use of ion gantries is very limited. The pioneering centre of HIT (Heidelberg Ion Therapy centre) has been

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the first to install an ion gantry, still the only one in Europe [6]. This gantry is based on classical resistive magnets, it has a length of 25 m and a weight of about 600 tons (rotatable part) and entered into operation in 2012. A layout of the facility is shown in Figure 3.

A technology breakthrough has been performed at the HIMAC centre in Chiba (Japan), where a gantry based on superconducting magnets is in operation since 2018 (Figure 1). This gantry weighs about 350 tons and it is half the length of the Heidelberg one. It was developed by Toshiba company. This gantry is based on cos-theta combined function magnets. The maximum dipole is 2.88 T, while different gradients, up to 9 T/m, are introduced. The small momentum acceptance of the system necessitated the use of low AC-loss Nb-Ti wire, with 10 μm filaments. The magnets are conduction cooled with 1.5W/4.2K cryocoolers.

A further reduction of size and weight, and of the cost, would certainly enable a wider diffusion of ion gantries, thus contributing to better coverage of the territory by ion therapy centres. The use of accelerator magnets of the type developed for High Energy Physics (HEP) colliders, with relatively small weight and strong field in a narrow long pipe, can help to make the breakthrough toward low weight, low-cost ion gantry. In this respect, Toshiba is currently studying a novel HTS-based gantry, aiming at a further reduction of size and weight.

Figure 3: Layout of the HIT facility in Heidelberg, Germany. Reprinted from [6].

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3 Targets for gantry and accelerator magnet designs

This document focuses on the choices of demonstrator magnet layout and conductor material. For this reason, it has been concluded that straight-magnet designs are sufficient for comparison, thus avoiding the difficulties arising from curvature. As mentioned in Section 2, the main challenge of this project come from the adoption of superconducting magnets. The main aspects driving magnet requirements are the momentum acceptance and the cooling system. They are both briefly discussed in this section, and the reader is again referred to [5] for further discussions.

The main design parameters have been established as common values with two other ongoing programs, IFAST [7] and SGRUM [8] (with the related INFN-SIG program [9]). This will allow a fruitful collaboration, with a wider study of magnet design and construction.

The demonstrator under investigation in this document is required to provide 4 T, for a 1.65 m bending radius, plus an additional 5 T/m gradient for curvature-effects correction and larger momentum acceptance. The physical length has been fixed to 1 m, aiming at a magnetic length of 0.8 m, to have a good compromise between the size of the flat field region (needed for magnetic field assessment) and the cost of the demonstrator, because longer magnet means more conductor and/or costs. The bore is fixed at 80 mm diameter. The loadline margin has been established around 25% at the nominal temperature. An iron yoke (cold iron) is expected in the final magnet for two main motivations: for shielding the stray fields and as a collar-support system. Table 1 summarizes the main magnet parameters discussed in this section.

3.1 Momentum acceptance for gantry

The problem of momentum acceptance is discussed here for proton therapy, but the same principle holds also for carbon ions. During a typical treatment session, a proton beam energy may need to be varied from 70 to 250 MeV, mainly to adjust the target depth. For protons, this means doubling the magnetic rigidity (from 1.23 to 2.43 Tm), so that the magnetic field of the bending dipoles must be tuned accordingly. In fact, a typical dipole magnet, at a fixed field, can accept variations in the beam momentum $p = m_0\gamma v$ of the order of $\Delta p/p=1\%$. This limited acceptance is related to the fact that beams entering the magnet at different energies will follow different path and exit the magnet at different points (and angles). In a light-optics analogy, this can be thought of as the variation in focal length for different wavelengths when passing through a lens. This dispersion can be tolerated up to a certain threshold, thus the stated 1%.

Tuning of gantry magnets has to be done in the order of 100 ms, approximately 50 times per treatment. This leads to magnetic field sweep rates around 0.15 T/m or higher. This is a reasonable demand for normal-conducting magnets, but easily causing instabilities in superconductors. Therefore, in order to mitigate the demand for such fast variations, solutions with larger acceptance are adopted. The most common one is the so-called achromatic bending, which means that, ideally, beams at all the required energy levels exit from the magnets in the same point and at the same angle (a light-optic analogy can be drawn with achromatic lenses). Achromatic solutions, listed by an expectable increasing momentum acceptance, are mainly three: to have two 90° bending dipole with a quadrupole in between, to adopt combined-function magnets, to design magnets with particle-tracking simulations and prescribe a nonlinear bending function. The larger the momentum acceptance (some solutions strive for $\Delta p/p=50\%$), the fewer are the changes in field level, up to no required tuning at all.

The demonstrator under investigation adopts the combined-function solution, with a single gradient added to the dipole field. To widely address the aforementioned issues, a ramp-rate of

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0.4 T/s is also demanded for the demonstrator. Once the design of the gantry is further defined, it will be possible to better address the momentum acceptance problem.

3.2 Cooling system

The operation temperature is expected to be between 4.7 K (LTS) and 10 K (HTS), so that the magnet will be cooled in helium gas or fully cryogen-free, i.e., cryocooler with solid conduction). This is motivated by the fact that cooling with liquid is not possible due to the rotation of the structure. The idea of having a ramped magnet without liquid helium is adding further challenges to the project. A wider momentum acceptance magnet, which demands small or virtually zero ramp rate, would be beneficial to thermal design, but this aspect is postponed to the following tasks.

Cooling system is imposing constraints also on the managing of electrical power: a higher-inductance, lower-current design is to be preferred to reduce as much as possible the heat leaks from current leads. Therefore, all the designs aim at a nominal current of a few kA for the 4 T field.

Finally, the need for liquid-free cooling has an impact also on the choice of superconductors. As reported in [5], reaching even only 3 T may be a very challenging task without liquid Helium. For this reason, this document also discusses solutions with HTS, where higher temperatures and larger temperature margins can be achieved.

Table 1. List of target parameters for the design proposals comparison

Parameters	Values	unit
Geometry	Straight, combined	-
Central magnetic field B_0	4	T
dB/dt	0.4	T/s
Magnetic and physical length	0.8 and 1	m
Bore diameter	80	mm
Operation temperature	4.7 ÷ 10	K
Iron	Shield +support	-
Loadline margin (@4.7 K) static	25	%

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4 Designs and comparison

This section covers the main aspects of the different designs developed in Task 8.1. Most of the proposed designs are based on canted-cosine-theta (CCT) layouts. This solution was firstly proposed in the '70, but it has re-gained interest in recent years for a series of reasons, ranging from the high field quality to the stress managements capabilities, to the need for less parts in magnet assembly. In the framework of ion therapy research, one of the most interesting features of CCT is the fact that it is possible to vary the harmonic content of the magnetic field along the magnet length. As an example, Alternating-gradient CCT have been proposed [10], with an expected momentum acceptance of 25%.

Three solutions with LTS are given with CCT layout. They all share same key features, such as grooves perpendicular to the cylindrical surface where conductor lies, for an easier machining (at least for straight prototypes). Iron yoke is added for both field enhancement and structural support. Therefore, a more detailed report is provided for the solution in Nb-Ti, while the subsections about Nb₃Sn and MgB₂ mainly highlight the peculiarities of each superconductor.

The CCT in HTS later proposed has some differences with respect to the others CCT, and it has undergone a different analysis, more focused on conductor features rather than the construction of an actual magnet. The reason is to be found in the fact that HTS are a less consolidated technology and further studies are foreseen in the following tasks of HITRI_{plus} project. Finally, a classical cos-theta design in Nb-Ti is proposed, for the sake of comparing it to the CCT solution.

4.1 CCT based on Nb-Ti

The first design option concerns a CCT layout based on Nb-Ti superconductor. The conductor is made of a rope with 6 Nb-Ti strands plus a copper core strand (Fig. 4). Table 3 reports the main cable parameters. As shown in Fig. 5, the magnet achieves the target dipole (4 T of bore field) and quadrupole fields (5 T/m of gradient), at nominal current @ 4.7 K temperature.

Table 2. Cable parameters – Rope (6 Nb-Ti wires +1 copper core wire)

Parameters	Values	unit
Type	Ropes (6+1)	-
Twist pitch	30 ÷ 50	mm
Rope current (4 T @4.7 K)	1308	A
Total current (4 T @4.7 K)	20928	A turns
J_{rope} (4 T @4.7 K)	275	A/mm ²
Insulating thickness	0.12	mm
J_{rope} (4 T @4.7 K) -insulated	228	A/mm ²
$J_{winding}$	161	A/mm ²

Figure 4. Cross section of the superconducting rope, 6 Nb-Ti strands + 1 central copper strand.

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The load line margin is 28.7% @4.7 K and 33.4% @4.2 K, bigger than the target 25% @4.7 K (Fig. 6); the critical temperature is 6.3 K (with a temperature margin of about 1.6 K). The magnetic length is about 0.73 m, slightly less than target 0.8 m, which is due to limitation of the total physical length of the magnet to 1 m. The field quality shows 6 units of b3, not critical at this stage, but to be improved for final design.

The mechanical design is based on two formers with a minimum rib thickness of 0.8 mm and grooves perpendicular to the cylindrical surface, for an easier machining. The materials considered for the former are aluminium bronze 954 and PEEK GF30 (polyether-ether-ketone, reinforced with 30% of glass fibres). Finite-elements simulations are performed. The stresses on the formers are well below the limit of both materials, resulting in a safety factor to yielding of 1.67 for PEEK GF 30 and 2.37 for aluminium bronze 954. The stresses on the conductor are estimated to be far (lower than 70 MPa in the worst case) from the yield limit of 300 MPa of Nb-Ti. In case of aluminium bronze 954, the radial displacements are of the order of 10 μm , while for PEEK GF30 they are of about 100 μm (which is acceptable even if somehow more than the typical value for cosine-theta magnets). Azimuthal displacements remain well below the 100 μm for both the materials (Fig. 7).

The protection analysis shows that the time windows for quench detection and protection activation are larger (0.325 s for a rope 6 Nb-Ti+1 copper strands, and 0.149 s for a rope 7 Nb-Ti strands) compared to a typical high field magnet target (100 ms for Nb-Ti magnets, and 50 ms for Nb₃Sn). The rope (6 Nb-Ti +1 copper strands) has a 17% more limit than the 7 Nb-Ti strands in terms of Quench Integral (QI). Both solutions are possible, but 6+1 is selected to increase stability.

During magnet ramping (at 0.4 T/s), the conductor losses due to persistent and interfilament coupling currents are bigger than 2 W/m at low field (0.45 T), while are less than 1 W/m at 4 T. The eddy-current losses from the metallic formers are the most significant ones (reaching 13 W/m). A proposed solution is to build the aluminum-bronze formers as two half shells (with a cut in longitudinal direction, i.e. along the beam path, at magnet poles), to be then assembled with a thin insulating layer in between. This would reduce the power losses to about 2 W/m, but a practical implementation has yet to be developed. The conclusion is then to pursue a plastic former, even if this decision may be revised in further stages of the project, because of thermal considerations. In fact, plastic materials are thermal insulators, which may interfere with the cooling of conductors. Preliminary calculation of the current leads power consumption, for a rope current of 1300 A, results in 120 W of cooling power to be supplied at 50 K by one cryocooler.

Figure 5. Magnetic Field map in the cross section and profile of B_y at center along z-axis. The zoom highlights the homogeneous field region of the B_y (200 mm at 0.1% of homogeneity).

Figure 6. Peak field load-line at 4.7 K and 4.2 K. The margin on the load-line at nominal bore field is 28.7% at 4.7 K and 33.4 % at 4.2 K. The critical temperature curve is reported at 6.3 K (temperature margin of about 1.6 K).

Figure 7. Radii in the CCT magnet geometry (left) where the radial displacements due to Lorentz force with Al-Br former (right) were evaluated.

4.2 CCT based on Nb₃Sn

Nb₃Sn superconductors offer two main advantages, compared with Nb-Ti: higher engineering current density and wider temperature margin. Nevertheless, Nb₃Sn is hard and brittle, fracturing at elongations of only 0.3% [11]. Therefore, wires are made by ductile precursors (CuSn, Nb) and the Nb₃Sn alloy is formed only after coil winding. The process consists of a

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heat treatment up to 700 °C. The need for this treatment imposes strict constraints on the choice of materials: the former must resist to the high temperature and match the thermal expansion of the wire. Therefore, aluminum-bronze is selected as the only candidate for the formers [12]. In fact, stainless steel also exhibits a thermal contraction similar to the conductor and outperforms aluminum-bronze in terms of mechanical strength, but it requires a more complicated machining. As discussed for Nb-Ti, aluminum-bronze is sufficiently strong for CCT.

Nb₃Sn superconductors are made by three main processes [13]: Bronze process, Internal-tin process, Powder-in-tube process. In general, Nb₃Sn by bronze process is not adopted for particle accelerator magnets. The reason is mainly related to the small critical current density achievable with this process, typically a third or even less of the ones from internal-tin or powder-in-tube. Nevertheless, the filament size is relevantly lower, at least nominally, with values in the range of 5 μm or less, against 30-60 μm of the other processes. The goal of the design is a nominal field of 4 T, to be reached with 0.4 T/s ramp-rate. Given that the critical current densities of bronze processed Nb₃Sn are still appreciably higher than the ones of Nb-Ti, and that the AC losses are of greater concern, the selected wire is made by bronze process. The selected wire for the Nb₃Sn design option is the Jastec L14/0.2/125. It is a round strand of 1.25 mm diameter, with approximately 14000 filaments of 4.8 μm nominal diameter. The ratio between non-superconductor and superconductor contents is around 4, resulting in $I_c = 279$ A @ 14T, 4.2 K. Data at lower field are not available and therefore Bordini's fit [14] is adopted to extrapolate. The estimated value is $I_c = 1450$ A @ 5T, 4.7 K. For comparison, the Internal-tin process strand ERMC-1 [15] is estimated to reach around 4000 A under the same conditions. Nevertheless, the expected performances of Jastec L14 are enough for a single-strand cable. The conductor is arranged in a canted-cosine-theta with a mid-plane tilt angle of 25°. The coil is made by 2 × 6 strands. Each strand is protected by a fiberglass sleeve of 0.15 mm thickness. As far as Nb₃Sn changes its volume during the heat treatment, an estimated +2.5% is added to the strand diameter in the final configuration, together with a few tenths of a millimeter for tolerances. The final groove is 3.5 mm width and 10.1 mm high.

Figure 8: Cross section (left) and margin on critical curve (right) for the Nb₃Sn CCT design.

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Thanks to the stronger and stiffer material employed (if compared with the Ni-Ti PEEK design), the formers have a spar of 4 mm width and ribs of 0.9 mm thickness. Grooves are prescribed to be perpendicular to the cylindrical surface, for machining. An additional aluminum-bronze shell of 5 mm width is added around the magnet. The goal is to have a structure which partially sustains itself, allowing for a relaxed design of the CCT-yoke interface. The only open point for the design, requiring further investigation, is the choice of the filling material. Mechanical finite-elements simulations have shown that common cryogenics epoxy resin as CTD-101K may start debonding from formers at temperatures around 150 K. The reason should lie in the different thermal contraction coefficient.

The iron yoke is at a radius of 73 mm with respect to the magnet axis and it extends up to 160 mm. For the sake of magnet assembly, a 30-mm-thick aluminum shell is placed around the yoke. The overall width of the magnet is 360 mm.

4.3 CCT based on MgB₂

Interest in MgB₂ superconductors has arisen due to their remarkably high critical temperature (40 K), despite their performances in terms of critical currents are limited. Therefore, a design fulfilling almost all the criteria for the HITRI_{plus} demonstrator is proposed. MgB₂, like Nb₃Sn, is hard and brittle, though with a larger parameter space where it can be employed. Depending on the minimum curvature radius required by coil geometry, MgB₂ may undergo a heat treatment before or after the winding. In the presented design, it is necessary to perform the treatment after the winding, since the winding radius requires a bending radius or the wires beyond the acceptable limit of MgB₂, (about 1%). Therefore, aluminium-bronze is selected as the only candidate for the formers.

A MgB₂ wire has been already employed by INFN-Milano-LASA in other projects. This is a 0.8 mm strand manufactured by Hypertech, with $I_c = 74 \text{ A @ } 5\text{T, } 4.2 \text{ K}$. In order to demand for a reasonable current from the power supply, a 6×2 Rutherford cable is proposed. Despite the relative novelty of the material, MgB₂ has been already employed in the fabrication of Rutherford cables of this layout and studies about degradation are available, [16], [17], [18]. The expectable degradation is about 30%. Considering a compaction factor of 0.89 [16], it can be shown that the engineering current density in the groove is similar to the one obtained by the stacking of single strands (insulated).

Reaching 4 T in the aperture requires certain un-optimized design choices. First, a lower tilt angle is preferred to reduce the peak field on the conductor, and 22° is selected. Secondly, due to the expected high temperature margin (estimated to be of 20 K), a load-line margin of 15% is accepted. The resulting coil is made by 4×8 Rutherford cables, with 67 A per strand (804 A per cable). The groove is $7 \times 46 \text{ mm}$. Due to the dimensions of the coil, the number of turns which can be accommodated in 1 m is too small to produce a sufficiently flat field distribution in the centre and therefore the mechanical length of the magnet is risen to 1.2 m.

In order to maximize the effect of the iron on the magnetic field, the formers have spar of 7 mm (with 0.9 mm ribs), while no external shell is foreseen, so that the mechanical assembly of the magnet follows the approach of the Nb-Ti design. Moreover, a wider yoke is adopted to finally reach the 4 T target. The inner radius of the yoke is 150 mm and the outer 250 mm.

Figure 9: Cross section (left) and margin on critical curve (right) for the MgB2 CCT design.

4.4 CCT based on HTS

A design based on ReBCO tapes is proposed, in the pursuit of future application of HTS. If compared with the designs presented in the previous sections, this CCT presents several aspects of novelty. This is motivated by the different features of HTS, if compared with LTS. In particular, the magnetic field is generated entirely from conductors. Moreover, due to the conductor geometry (tapes), the grooves of the former follow the Frenet-Serret path, avoiding hardway bending.

Two variants of the same design are developed, to evaluate two different options for magnet protection and quench detection. The first one, *No-insert* (N) prescribes only metal layers between the tapes, while the second option *Insert* (I) includes also copper layers. In both cases, the groove accommodates 14 cables of 2 tapes each. The main tape parameters are reported in Table 3. Each tape carries 780 A at 10 K, which implies that pairs of cables should be connected in series, so that the power supply demand is for 1560 A.

The mechanical design is based on two layers of 115 turns, with a pitch of 5 mm, and a spar thickness of 2 mm. This last parameter may be reviewed after a more detailed mechanical analysis.

Table 3. ReBCO tape parameters per cable

Option	Tape Width [mm]	Tape Thickness [μm]	$t_{\text{substrate}}$ [μm]	t_{copper} [μm]	t_{HTS} [μm]	$t_{\text{insulation}}$ [mm]
1 (N)	4	66	40	32.5	2.5	30
2 (I)		223		180		

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The main difference in the mechanics of the two options is the groove height, which is 2 mm for option N and 6.7 mm for option I. Both options, however, measure 1 m in length and provide about 0.75 m of magnetic length. Both guarantee a 29% loadline margin and an estimated 16 K of temperature margin. Figure 10 reports the local loadline margin in the conductors, while Figure 11 accounts for temperature margin.

The need for two options in the design come, as already mentioned, from protection concerns. Adiabatic hotspot criteria [19] applied to option N shows that even a time for detection-and-discharge of only 10 ms would result in temperature rising to 500 K, irretrievably damaging the magnet. A layer of 300 μm of copper per cable is estimated to be the minimum amount to guarantee an acceptable magnet protection with classical methods. For instance, reaching 266 K with a detection-and-discharge time of 70 ms. This is still a non-trivial challenge. In fact, threshold voltages of the order 10 μV are required to respect such timing, but they have to be detected in a 9.5 V voltage (during field ramps). Despite the conclusions drawn up to this point, it is reasonable to expect that the large temperature margin may provide enough safety during operation. Therefore, rather than adopting classical approaches, a protection base on temperature measurements to avoid quench at all may be a feasible solution. In this case, option I would be an unnecessary complication and no-insert option N may be preferred.

Figure 10: Loadline margin in the conductor for HTS CCT design (option 2).

Figure 11: Temperature margin in the conductor for HTS CCT design (option 2).

4.5 Cos-Theta based on Nb-Ti

A more classical cosine-theta layout has been studied for a direct comparison of advantages and disadvantages from the two Nb-Ti configurations. The same Nb-Ti strand used for the CCT layout has been adopted in a Rutherford cable solution, shown in Figure 12. The main parameters of the strand and the cable are reported in Table 4. A 5% degradation of the critical current density, used for the electromagnetic design, is considered to account for the effect of the cabling process on the Nb-Ti wires.

The magnetic field target of 4 T in the magnet bore is reached with a current of 3580 A and a 31.8 % margin on the load line. A magnetic peak field of 4.24 T is expected on the cable conductor in the higher turn of the first layer (in the magnet cross-section), see Figure 13. The margin calculation has been performed using the critical surface rescaled at 5 K of temperature, thus considering the increase of the operational temperature due to the power losses on the conductor. The temperature margin is equal to 1.65 K and the enthalpy margin on the overall insulated cable is 9.93 mJ/cm³.

The iron yoke has an internal radius of 70.8 mm to allow the inserts of a stainless-steel collar for the superconducting coil support during energization. The magnetic field quality has been calculated in the straight magnet configuration and no additional contribution due to the magnet curvature has been considered during the preliminary design process, consistently with the aims of this document.

Table 4. Strand and Rutherford Cable Parameters

Strand			Cable		
Parameters	Values	unit	Parameters	Values	unit
Material	Nb-Ti		Strands Number	22	
Strand Diameter	0.821	mm	Cable Width	9.9	mm
Alpha	1.36	Cu/CuMn0.5:Nb-Ti	Cable Thickness	1.362/1.517	mm
J _c @ (5 T, 4.22 K)	2185	A/mm ²	Insulation	0.102/0.125	mm

Figure 12: Rutherford Cable Geometry of the NbTi CT design

Figure 13. Magnetic Field Amplitude in the Magnet Cross Section

The major allowed harmonic b_3 is equal to 10 units and can be further improved with the cable positioning. Additional harmonics are expected to raise, due to the curvature of the magnet, within a couple of units as maximum limit and would be compensated with the coil ends spacing.

The transient losses occurring in the coils have been calculated on a preliminary electromagnetic design with a 70 mm bore diameter and a 4.5 T dipolar field. The total contribution from persistent, IFCC and ISCC losses is in the interval between 1.9 W/m and 0.7 W/m when the central field is ramped from 0.45 T to 4.5 T, with an average loss value of 1.1 W/m. The maximum coil temperature increase, located in the inner midplane turn, is of 340 mK when the iron is kept at 4.7 K. The highest temperature gradient is developed in the stainless-steel collar, see Fig. 14 left. Despite that, the minimum value of the critical current density is still in the inner pole turn, see Fig. 14 right, and it is reduced by 8% with respect to its value at 4.7 K.

Figure 14. Temperature and critical current density distributions in the cross-section

4.6 Indices for design comparison

This section provides a set of performance indices to orient the decision of the demonstrator design. As far as practically all the proposed alternatives comply with the target parameters, the comparison is based on the performances in terms of costs, power losses and consumption. Additionally, the main support materials are summarized in their mechanical and electrical behaviour, to provide additional information to the further developments of the designs.

4.6.1 Cost/efficiency of superconducting materials

The first comparison regards the amount of superconducting material needed to produce the desired field, in each design. The performance is expressed both in terms of financial costs and wire length. Moreover, the first index is the cost of 1 km of cable per carried current. Expressing costs per unit length characterizes the efficiency of the design, while the “normalization” by carried current highlights the efficiency of the material itself. Costs are expressed with an uncertainty range of $\pm 50\%$.

To highlight the efficiency of the design, also the total length of the conductor per tesla is reported. The graphical representation of the cost index shows that common LTS (Nb-Ti, Nb₃Sn) are the most effective, HTS are promising but still suffering from high raw material costs, while the MgB₂ is practically out of competition.

Cost-Performance chart

Table 5. Cost - performance of the magnet designs superconductors.

Magnet design (Conductor)	€/kAm	km/T	TOT k€
CCT (Nb-Ti – low losses)	4.61	1.46	6
CCT (Nb ₃ Sn – Jastec)	10.41	0.26	10
CCT (MgB ₂ – Hypertech)	73.53	6.97	139
CCT (HTS – ReBCO tape)	38.46	0.58	70
Cos-Theta (Nb-Ti - low losses)	1.24	6.15	5

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It is unarguable that a complete comparison of costs should include also the expenses required for the supporting structures. In particular, the formers for the CCT and the collars for cos-theta (assuming that, if present, iron yoke design would not change among the different options). Discussing the CCT, for both PEEK and Aluminum-bronze solutions, the straight designs are expected to come at almost the same cost. A very rough estimations suggests around 5 k€ for raw materials (PEEK or Al-Br tubes) and approximately 15 k€ for machining a former. They are thus non-differential costs among all the CCT solutions. However, since the final magnet is going to be curved, the manufacturing process has to be revised practically from scratches. Concerning the collars of cos-theta, even if the raw material should come approximately at 3 k€, the manufacturing and the assembly (with the expectable requirement of a press), are hardly adding up to a cost lower than the CCT formers. Again, however, a better estimation of cost cannot ignore a more detailed mechanical design.

As a final remark, if further design will pursue iron-less or iron-reduced solutions, the conductor cost will become dominant.

4.6.2 Power losses

The second comparison covers the critical aspect of power losses inside the magnet. Both superconductor losses and current lead power consumption are considered. Despite the fact that this document is not assessing the cooling system, it is regarded as essential to limit power losses. The Nb-Ti- and Nb₃Sn-based designs suffer from conductor losses less than 1 W/m @ 4 T, where the persistent current and interfilamentary current losses have been considered. On the other hand, the MgB₂ design presents very high losses due to the amount of conductor needed to reach 4 T, and due to the strand feature considered for the study. Unfortunately, the evaluation of the HTS design conductor losses is still ongoing (TBD).

Table 6. Conductor losses and current leads power consumption.

Magnet design (Conductor)	W/m conductor –@ 4 T	W – CLs power cons. from 300 K to 60 K
CCT (Nb-Ti – low losses)	0.88	60 x 2
CCT (Nb ₃ Sn – Jastec)	0.70	44 x 2
CCT (MgB ₂ – Hypertech)	36.80	37 x 2
CCT (HTS – ReBCO tape)	TBD	72 x 2
Cos-Theta (Nb-Ti - low losses)	0.70	165 x 2

The current lead power consumption is the other critical parameter for the designs presented. The equivalent power consumption is evaluated, just for the resistive part (between 300 K and 60 K), by the relation $\frac{P}{I} = 46 \left[\frac{W}{kA} \right]$ [20]. As reported by the Tab. 6, the four CCT designs show a power consumption for both current leads less than 150 W, i.e. cooling power that can be easily supplied by one cryocooler. Conversely, the cos-theta design presents a higher value (about 330 W) due to the high current fed into Rutherford cable, more challenging from the thermal design point of view.

4.6.3 Power supply requirement

Power supply is a non-neglectable cost of the magnet system, therefore solutions which minimize electrical requirements should be preferred. Static operations mainly demand for a

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certain DC current, while time-varying fields also require a certain voltage to be supplied. Therefore, nominal current and inductance at nominal current are reported. As already mentioned, lower currents should be preferred to reduce the heat produced by current leads.

Table 7. Inductance and current of the magnet designs.

Magnet design (Conductor)	Inductance L [mH]	Current I [A]
CCT (Nb-Ti – low losses)	107	1308
CCT (Nb ₃ Sn – Jastec)	119	960
CCT (MgB ₂ – Hypertech)	471	804
CCT (HTS – ReBCO tape)	55	1560
Cos-Theta (Nb-Ti - low losses)	8.7	3580

The Tab. 7 confirms the statement of the previous subsection: i) the nominal current of 3.5 kA (and the ramp rate > 350 A/s for 0.4 T/s) of the cos-theta design increases the cost of the power supply with respect to the other designs; and ii) the high inductance of the MgB₂ design due to the amount of conductor could be another constraint for the ramp rate (high voltage power converter for 0.4 T/s). The inductances and currents of the three CCT designs (Nb-Ti, Nb₃Sn and HTS) are in the same range of operation, and they don't show criticalities in terms of power converter specs.

4.6.4 Materials for supporting structures

Most of the proposed designs are already prescribed with a certain material for the supporting structures (formers or wedges, depending on the layout). Nevertheless, following tasks may review the proposed designs, including materials. The main materials considered during Task 8.1 are summarized below, comparing their mechanical stiffness against electrical resistivity. It may be noticed that AISI 316 steel has not been adopted in any of the presented design, despite being the best material in the following comparison. The motivation lies in the more difficult machining of the material, when compared with the other metals for such grooves that are deep and with thin ribs. The same reason explains the exclusion of other candidates, such as titanium.

Resistivities are expressed in a log scale as far as they span different orders of magnitude, and they are expressed relative to the resistivity of AISI 316. For this reason, PEEK is out-of-scale, and it is actually placed on the line indicated by the arrow.

It is possible to appreciate that Aluminum Bronze 954 provides a good trade-off among the two properties, explaining why it is the main metal considered in the proposed designs.

Notice that Copper has not been considered for CCT formers not only for its low resistivity, but also for its low yield strength.

Material properties

Table 8. Young modulus and resistivity of the studied materials.

Material	E [GPa] @ 4.7 K	σ_y [MPa] @ 4.7 K	ρ [$\Omega \cdot m$] @ 4.7 K
Aluminum 6082-T6	77.70	380.0	1.38E-08
Aluminum Bronze 954	114.40	340.0	1.00E-07
Copper	137.00	83.0	3.00E-10
AISI 316L	215.00	580.0	5.00E-07
PEEK	18.10	200.0	/

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4.7 Discussion over the design proposals

Different designs have been proposed for the demonstrator magnet. Most of the options adopt CCT layouts, given the promising advantages of the technology. Both LTS and HTS are considered, and a cos-theta design is also presented. In the context of expressing an indication for the demonstrator design, the preferred solution may be the CCT in Nb-Ti superconductor.

This paragraph covers the main reasons toward this direction.

The first element to consider is the actual state of the art of heavy-ion superconducting gantry. The already discussed gantry at HIMAC centre is for sure the main figure of merit to compare. In this respect, a CCT magnet with low-losses Nb-Ti is a reasonable trade-off between adopting a proven technology and pursuing tangible improvements.

Comparing the CCT and the cos-theta solutions, it can be appreciated that all the main aspects are considerably similar. Cos-theta is more efficient in the economy of the conductor, but at a level (around 1k €) practically negligible with respect to the costs of the magnet, not to mention the whole gantry. On the other hand, the costs of the mechanical structures may play in favour of CCT. Moreover, if a proper former for the CCT is selected, power losses can be expected of the same magnitude of cos-theta (also the adopted strand is the same). Another constraint for the cos-theta is the high nominal current (3.5 kA) that increases the current leads power consumption and the cost of the power converter with respect to the CCT – Nb-Ti.

Nevertheless, the aspect where CCT is more advantageous against cos-theta is the more flexibility in the design of field harmonics. As already mentioned, CCT allows for more elaborated combinations of field harmonics, opening to larger momentum acceptance designs. As far as the other options are concerned, Nb₃Sn is a very interesting alternative on paper, but the already mentioned need for heat treatment is a relevant technological concern. The more compact design and the larger temperature margin, compared with Nb-Ti, makes Nb₃Sn a candidate for an intermediate step in between Nb-Ti and HTS, even if a direct final adoption of HTS may be pursued. Vice versa, MgB₂ was investigated for the sake of completeness, but the target of 4 T is probably too high for this technology.

Finally, the proposed CCT in ReBCO tape may be regarded as a first elaboration of the magnet for a next generation gantry, but it comes with too many technological challenges and thus a Nb-Ti demonstrator is proposed.

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5 Conclusions

Workpackage 8 (*Superconducting magnet design*) of the European project HITRIplus, aims at a first technical and financial assessment of different magnet designs for carbon ion synchrotron and gantry complex. In this framework, Task 8.1 focuses on the development of a demonstrator magnet, and this document summarize the related activities.

First, a review of the importance and the prospects of heavy-ion therapy is provided, also mentioning the actual status of world-wide activities. Then, a brief discussion is given on the main technological challenges for magnets in heavy ions accelerators and gantries.

Among the mentioned aspects, the main open point for gantry magnets is the cooling system. As discussed in Section 3, the need for a non-liquid cooling system is challenging, especially aiming at a dipole field of 4 T. This demand can be mitigated with different approaches, ranging from large-acceptance designs to large-margin superconductors. These aspects, however, require an integration with the design of the gantry, and they are therefore to be fully faced in the following tasks of the project.

The main design parameters have been established as common values with two other ongoing programs, IFAST [7] and the TERA-CERN/NUMMS SIGRUM project [8] with the companion INFN-SIG program [X]. This will allow a fruitful collaboration, with a wider study of magnet design and construction. The basic parameters are: 4 T of dipole field, 5 T/m of quadrupole, 0.4 T/s of ramp rate, 1 m of physical length, 80 mm of bore diameter, at least 25 % of loadline margin, and the use of iron yoke as shield and collar.

Different designs have been studied in order to compare their performance, and for making it easier a straight geometry has been adopted. Most of the proposed designs are based on canted-cosine-theta (CCT) layouts, three solutions with LTS (Nb-Ti, Nb₃Sn and MgB₂) and one with HTS (ReBCO Tape). A more detailed report is provided for the solution in Nb-Ti, while the subsections about Nb₃Sn, MgB₂ and HTS mainly highlight the peculiarities of each superconductor. A classical cos-theta design in Nb-Ti is proposed, for the sake of comparing it to the CCT solution.

A set of performance indices to orient the decision of the demonstrator design has been established in terms of costs, power losses and consumption. Additionally, the main support materials are summarized in their mechanical and electrical behaviour, to provide additional information for further developments of the designs. Comparing the CCT and the cos-theta solutions, it can be appreciated that all the main aspects are considerably similar. Cos-theta is negligibly more efficient in the economy of the conductor, but on the other hand it presents a high current (about 3.5 kA) that increases the current leads power consumption and the cost of the power converter with respect to the CCT – Nb-Ti. Nb₃Sn is a very interesting alternative on paper, but the already mentioned need for heat treatment is a relevant technological concern. Vice versa, MgB₂ was investigated for the sake of completeness, but the target of 4 T is probably too high for this technology. Finally, the proposed CCT in ReBCO tape may be regarded as a first elaboration of the magnet for a next generation gantry, but it comes with too many technological challenges for a curved demonstrator.

Of course, the selection is base also on a many other considerations. In particular, we considered since the initial proposal of HITRIplus to pursue CCT is a novel, promising, route, less consolidated than Cos-theta at this stage, but very interesting to explore as possible alternative.

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This study has shown that a Nb-Ti based CCT design has favourable characteristics, when compared to other options, thus conforming the initial choice.

There we can conclude that this document **is providing a design proposal for a CCT based on Nb-Ti, suitable as the basis for the HITRI^{plus} demonstrator magnet.**

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